

SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING TO CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES IN VINH LONG PROVINCE, VIETNAM

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Abstract

This study aims to propose solutions to enhance the effectiveness of management accounting practices in construction enterprises located in Vinh Long province, thereby supporting managers in decision-making processes and contributing to improving business performance. Based on an analysis of factors influencing the application of management accounting, the study identifies six key determinants affecting the extent of implementation and the effectiveness of the system, including: (1) Market competitiveness; (2) Enterprise size; (3) Professional qualifications of the accounting staff; (4) Awareness and concern of top management; (5) Costs of organizing and operating the management accounting system; and (6) Business development strategy. The research findings provide a practical foundation for construction enterprises in Vinh Long to select appropriate management accounting models and offer policy implications for regulatory authorities to promote the adoption of management accounting in local enterprises.

Keywords: Management Accounting, Construction Enterprises, Vinh Long, Influencing Factors, Business Performance.

1. Introduction

In the context of a rapidly changing global economy, Vietnamese enterprises in general, and construction enterprises in Vinh Long province in particular, are facing intense competition, cost pressures, increasing demands for financial transparency, and the need to optimize operational efficiency. In this trend, management accounting (MA) is increasingly recognized as an important strategic management tool—not only supporting planning, control, and decision-making but also contributing to the sustainable development orientation of enterprises. MA provides a valuable information system that serves the processes of strategic planning, forecasting, and evaluating the performance of departments within an organization, thereby enabling managers to promptly adjust plans to achieve the set objectives.

Unlike financial accounting, which focuses on reflecting the financial position of an enterprise for external stakeholders, management accounting is aimed at providing detailed, specific, and highly predictive information for internal managers. Through the collection, processing, and analysis of data, MA assists management levels in cost determination, budget control, product pricing, investment evaluation, as well as measuring the productivity and efficiency of each department. The role of management accountants extends beyond recording and summarizing data to include consulting, forecasting, and strategic analysis—thereby enhancing the management capacity and adaptability of enterprises to market fluctuations.

In an increasingly complex and volatile business environment, the effective application of management accounting has become a key factor in maintaining competitive advantage. This is particularly significant for construction enterprises—a sector greatly influenced by fluctuations in material prices, project progress, and stringent project management requirements—where the adoption of MA plays a crucial role in optimizing resources, minimizing risks, and improving operational efficiency. Therefore, studying the application of management accounting in construction enterprises in Vinh Long province not only carries high practical significance but also provides a scientific basis for policymaking and improving corporate governance mechanisms in the current context of economic integration.

2. Research Results and Discussion

2.1. Research Results

Based on the synthesis of previous studies and adjustments tailored to the specific characteristics of construction enterprises in the local context, the author developed a research model consisting of six factors influencing the effectiveness of management accounting (MA) application. After conducting a survey and obtaining 195 valid responses from construction enterprises in Vinh Long province, the collected data were processed and analyzed using multiple regression methods.

Regarding the characteristics of the surveyed sample: 52.82% of enterprises had charter capital below 10 billion VND; 20% had charter capital between 10 and under 50 billion VND; 15.38% between 50 and under 200 billion VND; 6.67% between 200 and under 500 billion VND; and 5.13% had charter capital of 500 billion VND or more. This structure reflects the typical profile of construction enterprises in Vinh Long — predominantly small and medium-sized enterprises with limited financial resources.

The regression analysis results indicate that among the six proposed factors, five exert a positive influence and one exerts a negative influence on the level of MA application in construction enterprises. The order of influence, from strongest to weakest, is as follows:

1. Market competition intensity ($\beta = 0.353$);
2. Firm size ($\beta = 0.319$);
3. Accounting staff's professional competence ($\beta = 0.300$);
4. Top management's awareness of management accounting ($\beta = 0.297$);
5. Cost of organizing and operating the MA system ($|\beta| = -0.110$);
6. Business development strategy ($\beta = 0.105$).

These findings reveal that market competition intensity has the strongest impact on the adoption of MA. The higher the competitive pressure, the greater the tendency of enterprises to seek effective management tools to support rapid decision-making, cost control, and performance improvement.

Next, firm size shows a significant influence, as larger enterprises often possess more structured organizations, greater demand for multidimensional information, and stronger financial capacity to implement MA systems. Furthermore, the accounting staff's professional competence and top management's awareness also play essential roles, showing relatively similar levels of impact. When accountants are well-trained and top managers understand the strategic role of MA, the system can be applied more effectively in practice.

Conversely, the cost of organizing and operating MA systems is identified as a barrier to adoption, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises. Investments in software, personnel training, and maintaining specialized MA departments remain financial challenges for many businesses. Finally, the business development strategy has a positive but relatively modest impact, suggesting that MA is not yet viewed as an integral component of long-term strategic planning among many local construction enterprises.

2.2. Discussion

The research results are consistent with previous studies, both domestically and internationally, on factors influencing MA adoption. The finding that market competition exerts the strongest influence suggests that MA functions as a strategic tool enabling enterprises to adapt to competitive pressures — especially in the construction sector, where fluctuations in material prices, project timelines, and contractual risks are constant concerns.

The significant influence of firm size and accounting staff competence reinforces the notion that internal capacity is a prerequisite for MA effectiveness. Small enterprises often lack dedicated MA departments, and their accounting personnel tend to focus primarily on financial accounting, leading to limited management information. Therefore, improving accountants' skills and expanding operational scale will create favorable conditions for successful MA implementation.

The results also highlight the pivotal role of managerial awareness: if top executives perceive MA merely as a technical support function, investment in MA systems will remain limited. Conversely, if MA is recognized as part of strategic management, it can become the “heart” of decision-making processes.

Although implementation costs are a common barrier, in the long run, these should be viewed as strategic investments that deliver substantial benefits through resource optimization and enhanced risk control. Meanwhile, even though the business strategy factor shows a lower degree of influence, it remains crucial, as MA can only be truly effective when integrated with the enterprise's strategic objectives and sustainable development orientation.

In summary, the findings suggest that to enhance the effectiveness of MA adoption, construction enterprises in Vinh Long should not only strengthen their internal capabilities but also perceive MA as a strategic management tool that helps consolidate competitive advantages in a dynamic business environment.

3. Proposed Solutions

Based on the research results assessing the factors influencing the application of management accounting (MA) in construction enterprises, the author proposes the following solutions:

3.1. For the factor of market competition intensity

The stronger the market competition, the higher the feasibility of applying MA in Vietnamese construction enterprises. To survive and grow in a highly competitive market, enterprises must continuously improve the quality of their human resources, construction works, and services to meet the ever-changing needs of customers and the market — thereby increasing the demand for implementing MA systems.

Construction enterprises need to constantly update and analyze the needs and expectations of potential customers. This information should be compiled and reported to managers and executives so that they can formulate appropriate directions and strategies for product and service development, understand customer requirements, and propose suitable plans for each target segment. Enterprises can gather customer information through market surveys, post-service evaluations, and feedback mechanisms.

In addition, construction enterprises must also monitor the number and competitiveness of their rivals within the same market segment. This information is essential for developing corporate plans, responding promptly, and adapting effectively to competitors' actions. To obtain such data, enterprises can utilize social media platforms, newspapers, television, the internet, as well as attend industry seminars and events.

Competition acts as a positive driving force for the adoption of MA in Vietnamese construction enterprises. However, excessive competition may lead to negative effects on businesses. Therefore, regulatory authorities and relevant agencies should improve legal frameworks to ensure fair and healthy competition among enterprises in general and construction enterprises in particular, while preventing monopolistic practices by large corporations. At the same time, policies should be introduced to support small and medium-sized construction enterprises in enhancing their competitiveness, thereby increasing their capacity to adopt MA systems.

In today's era of broad international integration, the intensity of competition among enterprises is becoming increasingly fierce. This presents both opportunities and challenges for businesses in general and Vietnamese construction enterprises in particular. In a dynamic and promising business environment, enterprises must maintain their competitive advantages while expanding corresponding markets. To achieve this, enterprises should select and apply MA systems that best fit their operational characteristics, effectively manage and utilize existing resources, exploit new ones, and embrace innovation as a condition for survival and growth. These are essential prerequisites for promoting the adoption of MA tools among Vietnamese construction enterprises.

3.2. Regarding the Factor of Enterprise Size

Enterprise size is an internal factor that affects the ability of construction enterprises in Vietnam to apply management accounting (MA). Consistent with many previous studies, this research concludes that enterprise size has a significant influence on the implementation of MA in general, and in construction enterprises in particular. In practice, the larger an enterprise, the greater its management needs. With stronger financial capacity and the need to establish a more robust internal control system, large enterprises are more likely to succeed in implementing MA.

Moreover, these enterprises must manage a massive volume of information — not only internal data but also information about the business environment, market fluctuations, and competitors — making the MA system indispensable. However, there are clear differences between small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and large enterprises in terms of workforce, capital, and revenue. For small enterprises, particularly micro-enterprises, the application of MA may not be essential. Nonetheless, business owners or chief accountants can still apply basic MA tools at a simplified level.

Additionally, enterprise size also affects the operational efficiency of the MA system. Clearly, when comparing a larger enterprise with well-defined departments and a systematic MA framework, not only does it have a higher demand for MA, but it also possesses better resources, leading to a more professional and higher-quality MA system than smaller firms. A good working environment with transparent and well-organized information will motivate employees to perform better, create more value, and drive further business development.

Therefore, competent regulatory authorities should assess the needs and capabilities of enterprises of different sizes to promote the development and application of MA within Vietnam's construction sector. Instead of focusing solely on expanding total assets, construction enterprises should strengthen cooperation and foster linkages between large firms and SMEs. Through such collaboration, smaller enterprises will gain stable output markets, learn general management experience — particularly in applying MA — improve construction quality and management measures, and reduce competitive pressure. Smaller firms will gradually expand in size, while larger enterprises will continuously refine their management systems.

Large enterprises need to comprehensively apply MA to record and evaluate the efficiency of purchasing goods and services from smaller firms. Meanwhile, rapidly growing SMEs should also develop their MA systems to assess operational performance and support accurate managerial decision-making within their own organizations.

3.3. Regarding the Factor of Accountants' Professional Competence

Information provided by the accounting department is crucial for business managers. Accounting data not only reflects a company's financial status but also provides key figures that help leadership forecast trends, optimize costs, and enhance business performance. Therefore, accountants must possess sufficient knowledge and skills to collect business data accurately and apply MA tools to process it systematically.

In a highly competitive and rapidly changing business environment, accountants in construction enterprises must continuously update their knowledge, adopt new technologies, and apply modern management processes to improve the effectiveness of information provision within the MA model. Keeping up with the latest digital technologies and integrating them into accounting practices can significantly enhance the efficiency and timeliness of MA information.

To improve this factor, construction enterprises can hire management accounting experts to train their staff through reputable and high-quality programs, ensuring employees stay updated with the latest knowledge. Alternatively, firms can organize internal training sessions to facilitate knowledge exchange and experience sharing among accounting staff. Furthermore, construction companies may collaborate with universities and academies to design MA training programs that provide human resources aligned with business and industry needs.

In addition, enterprises should establish clear and specific criteria for accounting positions in their recruitment processes. Defining qualifications, skills, and experience standards will help businesses attract and select competent candidates, ensuring long-term stability and high-quality accounting personnel. This approach will enable construction enterprises to maintain sustainable growth and effectively face future challenges in an increasingly volatile business environment.

Moreover, businesses should build accounting teams that not only possess strong professional expertise but also have a deep understanding of their industry's characteristics and their company's business operations. This enables them to make accurate evaluations and analyses based on MA information, thereby producing more relevant and high-quality reports.

Creating a strong corporate culture — particularly one that fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing — is also vital. Experienced accountants with solid management and economic backgrounds should mentor less experienced colleagues. At the same time, professional ethics are critically important. Enterprises should establish confidentiality agreements requiring accountants not to disclose trade secrets or sensitive company information. Additionally, all information provided must be reliable, truthful, and objective, accurately reflecting the company's real situation, thereby serving as a sound basis for managerial decision-making.

3.4. Regarding the factor of senior management's awareness of management accounting

Senior managers play a vital role in any enterprise. They are directly responsible for directing and making decisions for the company, aiming toward continuous and sustainable development that meets the demands of the modern era. The more knowledgeable senior managers are about management accounting (MA), the greater the likelihood that MA will be effectively applied in construction enterprises. Having a system that supports managers in decision-making is essential. When these managers recognize the importance of MA and understand how to apply it to support business operations, helping the enterprise achieve its goals and mission, this factor is significantly improved. Therefore, enhancing managerial knowledge through specialized training programs for senior managers is crucial in changing their perceptions of the usefulness and benefits of MA tools in construction enterprises.

Accordingly, the Vietnam Association of Accountants and Auditors (VAA) and the Vietnam Association of Corporate Directors (VACD) should organize workshops, courses, and other relevant activities for businesses in general and construction enterprises in particular to enhance their ability to apply MA, thereby bringing MA closer to construction enterprises. Organizing specialized workshops, training sessions, and professional programs for senior managers will help improve their professional knowledge and ability to apply MA in business operations. This not only raises awareness of the importance of MA but also enables managers to better understand how to use this tool to optimize production, reduce costs, and improve business performance. For construction enterprises, adopting MA helps them gain better control over financial and management aspects, enhances transparency and operational efficiency, and supports sustainable business development.

To strengthen the application of MA systems in construction enterprises, senior managers need to have a long-term plan for investing in human resources and infrastructure. In terms of human resources, enterprises should implement continuous and regular training programs, including participation in courses, seminars, and information exchange to learn from external experiences and stay up to date with the latest information on MA systems. Additionally, managers should establish effective internal control systems to optimize the effectiveness of MA implementation within the enterprise.

3.5. Regarding the factor of costs for organizing a management accounting system

The cost of organizing MA in Vietnamese construction enterprises is a factor that negatively affects the adoption of MA. Research shows that the cost of implementing MA is inversely related to its feasibility — the lower the cost requirement, the higher the feasibility of applying MA. For Vietnamese enterprises in general and construction enterprises in particular, a major barrier to MA adoption is the concern about high organizational costs, while the benefits may be difficult to measure concretely.

For some enterprises, not applying MA and focusing only on financial accounting may help save costs; however, this approach fails to meet the information needs and competitiveness requirements of the business. Therefore, enterprises should consider investing in MA implementation suitable to their financial situation to balance financial capacity, expected benefits, and sustainable development. In the long term, increasing investment in MA may be necessary to ensure that accounting activities operate efficiently and align with the enterprise's strategic direction. Thus, combining financial accounting and MA at an appropriate level is essential to serve the enterprise's development goals.

Investment decisions regarding MA costs should take into account both internal and external factors such as enterprise size, corporate culture, and short- and long-term development prospects. The organization of MA should be based on a cost-saving mindset while maintaining high efficiency. Costs should primarily focus on acquiring equipment, accounting software, and technology for system building, as well as training and recruiting staff for MA application. For small-scale construction enterprises, initial investments in MA systems may not be large; they can start by adopting simpler MA tools such as cost management, profit analysis, and cost-benefit analysis. At the same time, they should make the best use of existing resources to gradually build and improve their MA systems. This approach enhances competitiveness, supports sustainable development, and creates opportunities for future business expansion.

3.6. Regarding the factor of business strategy

This is the factor that has the lowest impact on the ability of enterprises to apply management accounting (MA) among the six identified factors. Since 91.28% of surveyed enterprises have a scale of less than 50 billion VND, most of these businesses pay little attention to long-term business strategies and primarily focus on short-term operations.

However, in the current competitive environment, enterprises must change their business mindset to survive and develop amid increasing market competition.

Construction enterprises need to establish a clear strategic development orientation based on their strengths, weaknesses, and corporate mission. They must ensure flexibility in transforming business activities to adapt to customer preferences and general market trends in the construction industry. To ease the pressure of management, these enterprises require MA tools that allow them to be more agile in making strategic decisions for the short, medium, and long term.

A well-defined business strategy not only creates management demands but also provides a foundation for smoother application of MA in construction enterprises. To build an effective business strategy, enterprises need to study the needs of potential customers in their target market segment. They should establish a quality management system to ensure construction quality, compliance with technical standards, construction and acceptance requirements, and continuously improve the quality of projects. Moreover, they need to research competitors within the same market segment to develop appropriate strategic responses.

When considering and selecting business strategies, enterprises in general — and construction enterprises in particular — should focus on several key criteria such as low cost, differentiation, and core strategic objectives. In particular, differentiation strategies require businesses to possess distinctive attributes or provide outstanding products. Enterprises must be agile in seizing opportunities, overcoming market challenges, leveraging strengths, and minimizing the negative effects of weaknesses. Therefore, an effective MA system is essential to collect, process, and analyze information to support managers in making timely and suitable strategic decisions, ensuring product quality that meets market and customer requirements.

4. Conclusion

Management accounting plays a crucial role in assisting managers with decision-making and improving business performance, especially in the context of intense competition and an ever-changing business environment. For construction enterprises in Vinh Long Province, the application of MA not only helps control costs and optimize resources but also provides a foundation for strategic management and sustainable development.

The research identified six key factors that significantly influence the level of MA application in enterprises, including: (1) market competitiveness, (2) enterprise scale, (3) accountants' professional qualifications, (4) senior management awareness, (5) the cost of organizing MA systems, and (6) business strategy. Based on the analysis of these factors, the study proposes several key solutions such as: improving awareness and professional capacity of management accountants; strengthening the application of information technology in data collection and processing; optimizing the cost of MA system organization; and integrating MA with the enterprise's long-term strategic goals.

Implementing these solutions in a synchronized manner will enable construction enterprises in Vinh Long to fully harness the benefits of management accounting, thereby enhancing competitiveness, improving operational efficiency, and contributing positively to the local socio-economic development.

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